

Implementation of Line Impedance Stabilisation Network through Experiential Learning

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Abstract— In this paper an attempt is made to design and implement the Line Impedance Stabilisation Network (LISN) using the discrete components and to study its characteristics in comparison with the commercially available LISN. The aim of this work is to explore the use of LISN on quality of the signal and Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) and to implement a low-cost alternative to the commercial LISN available. The real-time implementation of the LISN design considerations is dealt with, demonstrating its role in Electromagnetic Compliance (EMC) testing, as a part of teaching learning process during the course delivery on Electromagnetic Compatibility. It was found that the results attained from the implemented LISN were comparable to the commercially available LISN.

Keywords— Line Impedance Stabilisation Network (LISN), Electromagnetic Interference (EMI), Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC), conducted emission, Standards.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electronic circuits are extensively used these days in various domains like automation, computations, communication and lot more. This may necessitate several diverse circuits to operate in close vicinity with each other, affecting each other to a great extent. Hence, Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) is the major concern for the electronic systems designer. For the system or the product designed, to be operative, Electromagnetic compatibility needs to be addressed with that of the government regulations. Therefore, EMC becomes the main design objective [1].

The regulating bodies are mainly concerned with the radiated emission and conducted emission of the product. Radiated emissions are the fields radiated from the device which would cause interference in the nearby devices. For compliance, the radiated emission measurements are carried out in an anechoic chamber or in open area test site. Conducted emissions are the currents that pass out through the AC power chord of the component into the common power network. These undesired conducted emissions are measured for compliance by inserting the Line Impedance Stabilisation Network (LISN) into the AC power cord of the unit. The current passes through the AC power line into the LISN that measures the interfering current and convert it to voltage. Conducted emission covers the frequency range of 450 kHz to 30MHz according to Federal Communications Commission (FCC) registrations and 150 KHz to 30 MHz as per International Special Committee on Radio Interference (CISPR) standard [1]-[4].

Line Impedance Stabilisation Network (LISN) is used to create a known impedance for measuring conducted emission. It finds its applications in test labs and automotive industries and behaves as a low pass filter, typically connected between the power source and the product under test (PUT). Other uses of LISN includes isolating the undesired RF signals from the power source, predicting the conducted emission during the compliance and pre-compliance testing and in immunity testing. Being used extensively in the field of Electromagnetic Compatibility, the concept of LISN is studied through an attempt to design a low cost LISN as the part of the teaching – learning process of the undergraduate course.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

D. Sakulhirirak et al. [5] have presented the study on LISN in compliance with the CISPR 16-1 standard. The paper outlines the design for $50\Omega/5\mu\text{H} + 5\Omega$ v-network through PSpice simulation. The paper highlights the importance of good impedance for in-house testing with the evaluation of impedance characteristics of inductors and capacitors at standard frequency of 150 KHz to 30 MHz. The simplified LISN that complies with CISPR 16-1 standard is presented. All paragraphs must be indented.

J. R. Nicholson et al. [6] emphasises the importance of the power line impedance in the measurement of conducted interference. Line impedance stabilisation networks (LISN) and its role in stabilising the power line impedance for the consistent measurement is discussed. Overview of the types of LISN is provided along with its applications. The paper highlights the role of power line impedance along with the use of LISN for precise measurement of the EMI interferences.

D. Sakulhirirak et al. [7] presents the design and analysis of the LISN that provide a standard $50\ \Omega$ impedance at a frequency range of 150 kHz to 30 Mhz. Paper throws light on the design of the air coil inductors based on the self-resonant frequency response concept. It provides the details of design process that includes the selection of the passive components, simulation of the LISN and the result verification.

I. Grobler et al. [8] presents the extended pre-compliance measurement setup developed for the conducted EMI measurement ranging up to 100 MHz, with no spectrum analyser being used. Noise signal from the LISN are then digitally observed using an oscilloscope and processed on the personal computer for the extraction of common mode (CM) noise and differential mode (DM) noise components. The setup was designed for development of power converters to verify the EMC design and test methodology.

J. Stahl et al. [9] presents the modification and characterisation of the LISN for effective separation of the common mode and differential mode noise in EMI filters. The separation setup being integrated into the LISN is described which requires the characterisation of the entire setup including LISN. The technique proposed provides high rejection of unwanted noise components and aids noise diagnosis and filter design. The utilisation of two current probes inserted into V-LISN not only simplifies the process but also measures the common mode and differential mode noise effectively.

A. B. Abinaya et al. [10] presents the design of LISN using the low pass filter to stabilize the input impedance and band pass filter to allow the frequency range of 150 kHz to 30MHz. The LISN is designed using the ADS software and is said to provide good impedance, cost effective compared to commercially available one and meet the CISPR-22 standard.

L. Wan et al. [11] investigates the limitation of applying the LISN for conducted emission in the low frequency range of about 2 to 150 kHz and proposes the possible solution. The increased amount of conducted emission to the power distribution system may be due to the switching behaviour and may impair the operation desired. As per the EMC standards, LISN does not fully take this range into account, resulting in inaccurate measurement. Three main limitations, namely unstable impedance with the variation of supply utility impedance, poor isolation between utility and DUT, poor coupling to receiver port at low frequencies are investigated. A possible solution is proposed that attaches two adapting breakout boxes containing a low pass filter and a high pass filter at main side and output side respectively of the present LISN topology at this low frequency range.

R. Amjadifard et al. [12] introduces a low cost multistage LISN to measure the conducted noise for DC-DC converters. The values of some parasitic elements were modified using suitable approach. This simple $5\mu\text{H}$ LISN provides sufficient isolation between input and output terminals. It is said to have good accuracy over the desired frequency range. The LISN proposed was verified using Advanced Design System simulation and is said to have good output characteristics in specified range.

L. Wan et al. [13] presents the two-stage cascaded filter LISN topology, designed to address the low frequency measurement that is not addressed by the CISPR standards. The prototype of the LISN was manufactured and characterised and proved to have improved performance in terms of impedance, voltage division factor and decoupling factor.

G. Kiraz et al. [14] presents the comparison of performance measurements of LISN calibration setup in a frequency range of 9 KHz to 100 MHz between four methods. These methods included vector network analyser (VNA), VNA tools, LCR meter and oscilloscope-current probe devices. Impedance measurement using LCR meter and oscilloscope setup were based on voltage and current applications. They were found to be more precise and stable up to 2 MHz Using oscilloscope and current probe measurement, impedance magnitude and phase components were obtained using voltage and current measurement over the LISN impedance. Measurement could be taken up to 20MHz. Measurement using VNA was based on applying the electromagnetic power to the DUT and found to have a measurement time advantageous than other methods.

III.IMPLEMENTATION

The circuit diagram of the low cost LISN set up was simulated using open source LTspice simulator. It is a graphic design software accessible freely that enables the circuit diagrams to be created easily. Developed by Analog Devices, it is a high-performing SPICE-based analog electronic circuit simulator capable of drafting, probing, and analysing the performance of the circuit designs. It has an extensive library of macro models and passive components and allows to configure each component individually.

At the power frequency, the capacitors of LISN appears like open circuits while the inductors of LISN appears like short circuits. The equivalent circuit appears like the DUT is connected to the main supply directly. During the frequency range of 150 KHz -30MHz, as per CISPR 22 standard the capacitors look like short circuits while inductors look like open circuits[1][3]. Hence, LISN isolates the external noise from the power network interfere the DUT operations in the first case, while in second case, provides the constant impedance in frequency, isolates the currents on power lines. LISN stabilises the impedance seen by the DUT looking at the AC power chord [1], [3]. Fig. 1 shows the LISN inserted into the setup.

Fig. 1: Block diagram of the LISN setup

Fig. 2 circuit diagram of LISN [5]

The circuit of the LISN employed for conducted emission is shown in Fig. 2. The currents that are to be measured for conducted emission, occur on supply lines. The conducted noise present at the supply terminal of the Device Under Test (DUT) is measured at the BNC connector connected to the spectrum analyser.

LISN is connected between the mains and the DUT. The series inductors are used to provide a low impedance at 50Hz for normal power delivery and a high impedance at the frequency range of typically 150 kHz to 30 MHz, blocking the flow of noise signals to the mains. The line-to-ground capacitors offers the low-impedance RF path to the ground. The main part of the LISN includes the equivalent resistive divider offering the 50 Ω path, DC blocking capacitor and the output connector. They are used to provide the standardised impedance to the receiver, convert the noise currents to measurable voltage and to block the main voltage to the analyser. Thus the circuit is designed to direct the conducted emission from the DUT to the standardised 50 Ω path and to isolate the DUT from the mains at RF frequencies. Fig. 3 shows the experimental setup implemented as an alternative to the commercially available LISN.

Fig. 3 experimental setup of the study on LISN

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

LISN is said to exhibit the response similar to the low pass filter. Fig. 4 shows the response of the designed LISN connected between the mains and the DUT. The graph shows that LISN is working fine in the range 150 kHz to 30 MHz

The flat region in the low frequency range up to approximately 1MHz range indicate the stable LISN impedance. The sudden drop called the LISN transition region is said to be caused due to the LISN inductors isolating the mains and the internal parasitic components. The noise floor of approximately 55 to 60 dBm show that DUT conducted noise is low. Spikes in the region above 30 MHz is not in the compliance region.

Fig. 4 Response of the designed LISN

Fig. 5 Response of commercially available LISN

Fig. 5 shows the typical response of the commercially available LISN. Here the LISN is powered from the mains, with the DUT being powered off. The LISN is connected to the spectrum analyser. The response obtained is flat and stable with no conducted noise from the DUT. Good transition region show the proper functioning of the inductors and grounding. Low noise floor indicate that the interference from the DUT is very low. Comparing the two results it is shown that the designed LISN exhibits proper behaviour considered at its basic reference.

V. CONCLUSION

This work was carried out as the part of the project based learning to understand the theoretical concepts studied as part of the undergraduate curriculum. Though the result cannot be used to test for the compliance of the device with the standard, the graph obtained is close to the behaviour of that of the LISN obtained commercially. It was possible to study the basic purpose of the LISN and can be used as the low cost LISN for understanding the concepts taught during the course. Through this work we were able to obtain the response similar to that of the commercially available LISN. However, the design can be tested for the CISPR standards and can be adopted for the teaching learning process for the courses related to Electromagnetic Compatibility.

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